

PATHWAY TO ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY IN PAKISTAN: EVIDENCE FROM LMDI DECOMPOSITION ANALYSIS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14792099>

ABSTRACT

In recent time environmentalists and economists are more concerned about environment friendly growth rather than simple growth. The environmental consequences of anthropogenic economic growth are causing climate change around the globe. This paper empirically test the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis for Pakistan over the period 1970-2016 by employing the ARDL Bounds testing methodology in conjunction with logarithmic Mean Divisia Index (LMDI) decomposition approach to disentangle emission level from economic growth. Empirical results validate the EKC exist in Pakistan both in the long run and in the short run over sampled period in Pakistan. The empirical results of decomposition analysis shows that the population growth effect and economic growth effect are the main driving forces of positive changes in CO₂ emissions. CO₂ emissions are only minimized with energy intensity factor. According to the policy recommendations, replacing the conventional energy sources with renewable energy technology is the best strategy for achieving long-term economic growth in Pakistan without compromise for environmental sustainability.

Keywords: Environmental sustainability; carbon-reduction; economic growth; ARDL methodology; Decomposition analysis; Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

Scientific and technological advancements propelled the unprecedented success of human civilization in the twentieth century. Countries over the world are extracting more and more of natural resources for economic growth. This increase in natural resource use has raised serious concerns. Many countries are now aware that long-term economic growth necessitates a reduction in resource use, while human health demands that economic activity be increased while the effect on the environment be reduced. The 5th Assessment Report of Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) states that human activity, especially the use of fossil energy

to meet energy requirements has disrupted the global ecosystem and the consequences of these activities will be borne by the entire planet.

The goal of the talks between different nations at the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC21st)'s annual meeting is to reach an agreement between countries to limit greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions to a level where worldwide temperatures remains in the limit of 2 degrees Celsius (Pre-industrial level). 5th Assessment Report of IPCC states that effect of human activities on the environment system is clear (IPCC, 2013). The key factor among these human activities that produces greenhouse gases

and causes a increase in co2 emissions is energy use. Increasing the use of fossil fuels raises GHG levels, which contributes to the greenhouse effect and global warming. Since GHG emissions are called negative externalities, countries that produce high levels of GHG impose external costs on other countries. Developing nations are particularly vulnerable because they cannot afford to pay for disasters and losses. Carbon emissions are the major contributor (60 percent) of all greenhouse gases (Khan et al. 2004; Baloch et al.,2021; Awan, Abro, & ul Mustafa 2021). Higher economic growth necessitates a massive amount of energy use, which is an important part of economic development (Siddiqui, 2004). One of the major contributors to environmental pollution is increasing energy use from non-renewable sources. Increased energy consumption is wreaking havoc on the atmosphere by releasing CO₂ emission from energy-related sources. Energy consumption rises as output and consumption rise, resulting in a substantial increase in energy-related CO₂ emissions.

While Pakistan contributes just 0.8 percent to global carbon emissions and is ranked 135th among all countries when it comes to calculating its share of global emissions, it is facing severe climatic change consequences. Environmental degradation is expected to cost Pakistan's economy around 6% of GDP annually, and the country is ranked as the world's 12th most vulnerable country to climate change (Khan, et al. 2004). In most of Pakistan's urban areas, the existence of high particulate materials in the atmosphere is a severe concern. The nature of the atmosphere is deteriorating as a consequence of the burning of fossil fuels and increased motorization. Pakistan has faced energy shortages in recent years, unable to meet its demand. As a result, Pakistan could be an interesting case study due to its energy problems. There is a need to search out the connection between energy use and economic development for the case of Pakistan. Furthermore, when deciding on energy policies, the path of the unidirectional relationship between energy consumption and economic growth is critical. If the unidirectional relationship is that energy demand increases with the increase in economic growth, then policies should be made to

preserve energy and minimise carbon emissions. However, if the causal relationship is that energy use affects economic development, energy preservation policies can decrease economic growth.

Oil, coal and gas are the three primary energy sources of Pakistan; the use of gas and coal has increased in the last decade (fig.1). In 2013-14, gas accounted for 40.9 percent of overall energy consumption, with oil coming in second with 31.9 percent and coal accounting for 8.7%. Because of the rise in crude oil prices since 2001, there was a substantial decrease in oil consumption between 2000-01 and 2005-06. (GOP,2016). As a result, gasoline, which was an expensive source for the power sector at the time, was replaced with a less expensive source (gas). As a result of this rising trend in energy use, carbon emissions are also rising (fig.2). Carbon emissions are generated in the atmosphere because of using natural resources for electricity generation. Carbon emissions were 32 Ktoe in 1980 and 413 percent higher in 2013 after 33 years.

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A small amount of research has been done on EKC in Pakistan, and some studies have discovered that an environmental Kuznets curve exists in Pakistan's case (Nasir and Rehman 2011; Ahmad and Long, 2012; Hussain and Ali (2016). Other studies claim that the Kuznets curve for the atmosphere is only valid for the long run but not for the short run (Amjad, et al.,2015; Al-Mulali et al.2016; Rauf et al.,2018). Due to data limitations,

there are only a few studies on decomposition study of carbon emissions for Pakistan. These studies used the LMDI approach, and the findings indicate that intensity effect, structural effect, and activity effect are key factors that are causing major changes in emissions; however, the most significant effect is the activity effect (Attari et al., 2011; Khan and Jamil, 2015). Financial growth has yet to be integrated into EKC empirical research in Pakistan, according to the available literature. Financial growth is a critical factor in developing countries, and it is regarded as a significant factor that affects carbon emissions in a variety of ways. As a result, we will attempt to add value to the available literature by including the financial development sector in the EKC review in this report. Previous decomposition research studies have used a fixed base year decomposition technique. As a result, it is necessary to investigate the CO₂ emissions trend using the time series decomposition technique to obtain complete data from the historical perspective.

This analysis will use the above-mentioned assumption in order to verify the nature of the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) and decompose CO₂ emission into its driving factors. More precisely, we want to achieve the following goals: (1) empirically test the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis in Pakistan for the period 1970-2016 by applying the ARDL Bound testing method. (2) Decomposition analysis of carbon emissions into their driving forces for the period 1970-2016 by employing log mean Divisia index (LMDI) technique.

By including a financial development variable in EKC research and examining its effect on total carbon emissions in Pakistan, this paper will add value to the existing literature. For the period 1980-2013, the analysis will also decompose total CO₂ emissions into their various driving factors. For the case of Pakistan, previous studies have used a period-by-period decomposition. Attari et al. (2011) and Khan et al. (2015), for example, both studies use a fixed base year decomposition technique. The pattern of CO₂ emissions will be investigated using time series decomposition analysis in this report. In addition, the current research will consider the role of renewables in

decomposition analysis. The study employs the ARDL bound research method to evaluate the EKC theory for Pakistan from the period of 1970-2016. Furthermore, to find out the contributing variables of Carbon emissions the study has utilized the log mean Divisia index (LMDI) methodology.

The research is organised in the following pattern: a brief overview of studies on environmental Kuznets curves and decomposition analysis is given in part (2). The methodological approach and data sources are discussed in part (3). Analytical findings and result discussion is given in part (4). And finally part (5) concludes with a conclusion and future strategy recommendations.

2- Theoretical background

Researchers have been paying more attention to the link between the environment and economic growth in the last decade, and a detailed literature on the association between income growth and environmental degradation has emerged. Environmental pressure increases in the initial phases of economic growth and decreases as the economy matures, according to all of the reports. The “Environmental Kuznet curve” is a term used to describe this form of relationship (EKC). Economic growth and environmental efficiency, according to EKC, have an inverted-U relationship. Because of the greater use of natural resources at the start of industrialization, pollution rises at a faster pace, and people are more concerned with their employment and incomes than with their clean environment (Dasgupta et al., 2002). People begin to appreciate their environment in the advanced stages of industrial growth as their incomes increase in tandem with the economy's growth and emissions levels fall.

Most researchers claim that economic growth causes environmental deterioration, but that it can also boost environmental quality (Beckerman, 1992; Rehman, Abro, Mustafa, Ullah, & Khattak, 2021), and that in developed countries, economic growth can be an effective tool for improving environmental quality (Panayotou, 1993). The Environmental Kuznets Curve theory has been put to the test by examining the effects of various variables on environmental quality, such as financial liberalisation, energy usage, trade

openness, and economic development. Initially, Halicioglu (2009) discussed the impact of trade openness on energy consumption, economic growth, and carbon emissions. According to Tiwari (2011), commercial energy use is a critical source in attaining economic growth in developing nations. There is a positive effect of Energy consumption on economic growth and CO₂ emissions, but has a negative relation with population and capital, according to his findings.

Many researchers tried to search out the link between carbon emissions and real income in early studies on the EKC theory (Shafik and Bandyopadhyay, 1992; Shafik, 1994). They discovered that CO₂ emissions and economic development have a growing positive connection. Schmalensee, Stoker, and Judson (1998), on the other hand, refuted the above assertion and demonstrated that the connection between CO₂ emissions and economic development is "inverted-u formed." In point of view of de den Bergh, Opschoor and Bruyn van (1998), the "inverted-u-shaped" phenomenon was only temporary, and the relationship eventually became N-shaped. Friedl and Getzner (2003) discovered an N-type relationship for a single country using empirical data. The same relationship was discovered by Galeotti and Lanza (2005) for a community of countries.

The Environmental Kuznets Curve theory has been put to the test by searching out the effect of various variables on environmental quality, such as trade liberalization, economic growth, financial liberalisation, and energy usage. Initially, Halicioglu (2009) discussed the effect of trade liberalization on economic growth, carbon emissions, and energy consumption. According to Tiwari (2011), commercial energy use is a critical factor in achieving economic growth in developing nations. Commercial energy usage is an important part of the manufacturing process that increases CO₂ emissions. Energy use is linked to economic growth and CO₂ emissions, but it negatively impacts the population and capital. Congregado et al. (2016) investigate the nature of EKC using data from 1973 to 2015 and the methods suggested by Kejriwal and Perron. They enable various activities to take place over time and classify them by economic sector. The

findings show that EKC exists in the United States only when structural breaks are allowed.

Previous researchers have tried to focus on defining the variables that are causing changes in total CO₂ emissions, with the majority of studies concluding that the key contributor factors are the economic activity impact and energy intensity effects (Alves and Moutinho, 2013; Akbostanci et al., 2009; sun et al., 2012; Hye, ul Mustafa, & Mahmood, 2010; Nasab et al., 2012).

3. Methodological construction

3.1 Data

The data for EKC's empirical model came from the World Bank database in 2015. Energy consumption is calculated as kg of oil equivalent, CO₂ emissions as metric tonnes per capita, domestic credit to private investors as percentage of GDP, trade openness as percentage of GDP, While GDP per capita and FDI (foreign direct investment) (net inflows, BOP) are all expressed in current US dollars, based on market prices.

This research spans the years 1970 to 2016. The data consists of total energy consumption by fuel group and is recorded in the annual energy balance sheets of Pakistan's energy year book series. For the energy sources of gas, coal, oil and renewables, the data used in this analysis was converted to kilo tonnes of oil equivalent (ktoe). The data of carbon emissions (excluding renewables) is taken from the Energy Information Administration (EIA). Data on renewable energy use from 1990 to 2016 is taken from the International Energy Agency. Since CO₂ emissions data for renewables isn't available, data on renewable energy use is converted to CO₂ emissions using the formula given by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). Since there is no data on CO₂ emissions from renewables (primary solid biomass), we must measure it using the formula given by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC).

The thesis takes the following empirical path: (1) unit root analysis using Dickey and Fuller's (1981) non-stationary test. This test will reveal the maximum order of integration of the variable of interest. Pesaran et al. performed the cointegration bound testing analysis (2001). Finally, the

Granger causality test is used to determine if the variables are causally related.

3.2 Model specification

Our research closely resembles the approach used in a recent analysis (Ozturk and Acaravci, 2013). To analyse the long-run association between carbon emissions, energy use, economic growth, trade liberalisation, FDI (foreign direct investment), and FD (financial development) in Pakistan, a quadratic equation is established.

We have a functional form as

$$CO_2 = f(Y, Y^2, E, TO, DC, FDI) \quad (1)$$

$$CO_2 = a_0 + b_1 \ln E + b_2 \ln Y + b_3 \ln Y^2 + b_4 \ln TO + b_5 \ln DC + b_6 \ln FDI + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

Logarithmic transformation is carried out on right side of above equation (1)

The prior assumptions of equation (2), according to theory, are; the expectation of $b_1 > 0$. That is, energy consumption (E) has a beneficial effect on emissions (CO₂). B_2 is also predicted to be optimistic, as income rises, so do CO₂ emissions. The sign of b_3 will affirm the existence of EKC; if it is positive, it means that EKC does not exist; if it is negative, it means that EKC does exist. Both trade openness and domestic credit would raise CO₂ emissions, so b_4 and b_5 are likely to be good for developing countries. Finally, if foreign direct investment requires new green technology, b_6 is projected to be negative. Empirical research has yielded mixed results. Trade transparency, according to Nasir and Rehman (2012), raises CO₂ emissions by boosting economic development, and Halicioglu found similar results (2009). Foreign trade, on the other hand, improves environmental efficiency by introducing new technologies into domestic development, according to Shahbaz et al. (2012). According to Tamazian et al. (2009), financial growth allows developing countries to implement new technologies, produce environmentally sustainable products, and thereby improve the environment on a wide scale.

3.3 Stationary test

We have used ADF (augmented dickey fuller) technique to test for unit roots and to check whether variables are integrated of degree “0” or “1”. We may apply the error correction model

when we are confirmed that all variables are of the same integrated level. However, if the variables are integrated at different levels we use the ARDL method to examine the relationship between variables in the long run and also in the short run.

3.4 Test for co-integration (ARDL Bounds approach)

ARDL is used on a single equation, and will analyse the short run and long run association among the variables simultaneously. Narayan (2004) said that ARDL method is handy when sample size is small. Johnson and Engle-Granger techniques are not reliable for small samples.

Fundamentally, the ARDL bounds testing technique of cointegration consists of two steps for analyzing long-run association. First of all we check for the presence of long run association between all the series of the model. The following is the ARDL model for Eq. (1) is

$$CO_2 = \alpha_1 + \sum_{g=1}^{a_1} \alpha_{2g} \Delta CO_{t-g} + \sum_{h=0}^{b_1} \alpha_{3h} \Delta \ln E_{t-h}$$

$$+ \sum_{i=0}^{c_1} \alpha_{4i} \Delta \ln y_{t-i}$$

$$+ \sum_{j=0}^{d_1} \alpha_{5j} \Delta \ln y_{t-j}^2$$

$$+ \sum_{k=0}^{e_1} \alpha_{6k} \Delta \ln DC_{t-k}$$

$$+ \sum_{m=0}^{f_1} \alpha_{7m} \Delta \ln TO_{t-m}$$

$$+ \sum_{n=0}^{g_1} \alpha_{7n} \Delta \ln FDI_{t-n} + \beta_1 CO_{t-1}$$

$$+ \beta_2 \ln E_{t-1} + \beta_3 \ln y_{t-1}$$

$$+ \beta_4 \ln y_{t-1}^2 + \beta_5 \ln DC_{t-1}$$

$$+ \beta_6 \ln TO_{t-1} + \beta_7 \ln FDI_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{1t}$$

The first difference is denoted by Δ which is random error. The impact of energy usage and economic growth on CO₂ emissions will be investigated using this lin-log model. Independent variables include foreign direct investment, trade openness, and DC (domestic credit to private investors).

Bounds testing

The bounds test method used the Wald statistic/ the joint F-statistic, which is used to determine the long-term association between series.

Let's pretend we have a usable shape.

$$CO_2 = f(Y, Y^2, E, TO, DC, FDI)$$

$$CO_2 = a_0 + b_1 \ln E + b_2 \ln Y + b_3 \ln Y^2 + b_4 \ln TO + b_5 \ln DC + b_6 \ln FDI + \varepsilon$$

Now the null Hypothesis and alternative hypothesis for bound testing are as follow

$H_0 : b_1 = b_2 = b_3 = b_4 = 0$ (there is no long run association exist)

$H_1 : b_1 = b_2 = b_3 = b_4 \neq 0$ (long run association exist)

According to Pesaran et al. (2001) we reject the H_0 hypothesis When the measured Wald-statistic/F-statistic > than the upper bound value, suggesting that there exist a long run association. And we are unable to reject the H_0 hypothesis if the measured F-statistic/Wald statistic is less than the upper bound value and we conclude that there is no long run association.

3.5 Estimation methodology for decomposition analysis

The study begins with the definition of a function of total CO₂ emissions that must be decomposed into different factors in order to create an IDA. These 'factors' will monitor changes in total CO₂ emissions, as reported frequently by the Kaya persona (Kaya, 1990). This Kaya Identity has undergone some changes; for example, LMDI is now used in several studies (Nasab et al., 2012; Akbostanci et al., 2009; Mahony, 2013). LMDI is considered to be the most appropriate for decomposing carbon emissions in Pakistan due to its higher features.

Since we're interested in multiplicative decomposition, the multiplicative technique formula is:

$$C_{tot} = C_t / C_0 = C_{emc} C_{ffse} C_{int} C_{ypc} C_{pop}$$

C_{tot} represents the cumulative change in CO₂ emissions from 1980 to 2014. C_{emc} The change in overall CO₂ emissions due to the emission effect; the change in carbon emissions due to a unit usage of fossil fuels (oil, gas, coal and solid biomass). C_{ffse} Represents the shift in CO₂ emissions as a result of the economy's replacement of fossil fuel types; a technological consequence. C_{int} is an indicator of energy

efficiency, technical choices, change in behaviour, and change in people's lifestyles, as determined by the change in energy consumption relative to a unit change in GDP due to structural change. The change in total carbon emissions due to changes in economic activity is represented by C_{ypc} . C_{pop} depicts increases in carbon emissions as a country's population grows or decreases. The following LMDI1 formulae were derived from Ang and Liu (2001) and applied to each of the effects;

$$C_{emc} : \exp\left(\sum_i \frac{(C_i^T - C_i^0) / (\ln C_i^T - \ln C_i^0)}{(C^T - C^0) / (\ln C^T - \ln C^0)} \ln \left[\frac{F_i^T}{F_i^0} \right]\right)$$

$$C_{ffse} : \exp\left(\sum_i \frac{(C_i^T - C_i^0) / (\ln C_i^T - \ln C_i^0)}{(C^T - C^0) / (\ln C^T - \ln C^0)} \ln \left[\frac{S_i^T}{S_i^0} \right]\right)$$

$$C_{int} : \exp\left(\sum_i \frac{(C_i^T - C_i^0) / (\ln C_i^T - \ln C_i^0)}{(C^T - C^0) / (\ln C^T - \ln C^0)} \ln \left[\frac{I^T}{I^0} \right]\right)$$

$$C_{ypc} : \exp\left(\sum_i \frac{(C_i^T - C_i^0) / (\ln C_i^T - \ln C_i^0)}{(C^T - C^0) / (\ln C^T - \ln C^0)} \ln \left[\frac{G^T}{G^0} \right]\right)$$

$$C_{pop} : \exp\left(\sum_i \frac{(C_i^T - C_i^0) / (\ln C_i^T - \ln C_i^0)}{(C^T - C^0) / (\ln C^T - \ln C^0)} \ln \left[\frac{P^T}{P^0} \right]\right)$$

4. Results and discussion

To estimate the EKC hypothesis in Pakistan from 1970 to 2015, we first translated all of the series to log form because the GDP per capita and foreign direct investment series were so high in comparison to the small values of the dependent variable CO₂ emissions. To make it a Lin-log model, we convert the remaining explanatory sequence to log. Then, for each series, we applied the ADF (Augmented Dickey Fuller) test of unit root to determine whether it is stationary or non-stationary series. This will also serve as justification for using the ARDL or VAR techniques. The summary statistics for the ADF unit root test is given in Table (1). The results show that the $\ln TO$ and $\ln FDI$ series are level stationary, i.e. they are integrated of degree zero I (0), while the other series (CO_2 , $\ln DC$, $\ln EC$, $\ln GDP$, and $\ln GDP2$) are integrated at first level i.e. they are integrated of I(1). The results of ADF tests provide justification for the ARDL approach. We also look at all of the series' graphical representations to see whether data has any structural breaks, the data did not include any structural breaks.

Table1 Test of the stationarity for Series

Variable	Parameter	ADF cal	Prob.	Trend/Intercept	Inference
CO2	-0.57	-3.38	0.001	None	1 st difference
lnGDP	-0.73	-4.93	0.0000	None	1 st difference
lnGDP2	-0.75	-4.99	0.0002	Intercept	1 st difference
lnE	-0.84	-5.45	0.0003	Both	1 st difference
lnDC	-0.85	-5.56	0.0000	Intercept	1 st difference
lnFDI	-0.57	-4.17	0.0107	Both	Level
lnTO	-0.301	-3.33	0.0192	Intercept	Level

Source: authors compilation

To see if there is a long-term association between variables, we used the Bound Testing process. CO2 emissions, GDP, Square of GDP, energy consumption (E), trade openness (TO), DC(domestic credit to private investors), and FDI (foreign direct investment) all have a long-term relationship, according to the F-test for co-integration (See Table 2). The F-statistic value is

given in the second column. The lower and upper bound values are found in columns 2 and 3, respectively. The value of Wald-statistic/F-statistic "9.526" is > than the lower bound value of 3.15 even at a 1% α (level of significance), which means that we accept the H1 hypothesis and conclude that there is a long-run relation between the series.

Table2 Results of Bound Test for Co-integration

ARDL Bounds Test		
Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	9.526	6
Critical Values		
Significance level	Lower Bound value	Upper Bound value
10%	2.12	3.23
5%	2.45	3.61
2.5%	2.75	3.99
1%	3.15	4.43

The long-run effects of the EKC model are given in Table (3). CO2 emissions are the dependent variable, which is a proxy for environmental quality, while lnE, lnGDP, lnGDP2, lnFDI, lnDC, and lnTO are the independent variables. The results show that a 1% rise in GDP/capita increases carbon emissions by 0.0462 period, while the negative sign of GDP/capita square (GDP2) tends to confirm that carbon emissions begin to decrease once income reaches a certain level. This means that per capita CO2 emissions rise as real income rises to a certain point, after which they begin to decline as per capita real income rises. The Environmental Kuznets Curve hypothesis in Pakistan's economy is supported by these findings. Ahmed and Long (2012), as well as Shahbaz et al., support these findings (2012). According to the findings, a 1% rise in energy consumption would result in a 0.0039 period

increase in carbon emissions. CO₂ emissions are increasing as more fossil fuels are used to meet energy demands. Hussain and Ali came to the same conclusion (2016). The findings, on the other hand, indicate that Pakistan's trade liberalisation has no long-term effect on carbon emissions. These findings are consistent with those of Jayanthakumaran, et al. (2012), who found a positive association between foreign trade and CO₂ emissions, but it was not statistically important. Trade transparency, according to Nasir and Rehman (2012), raises CO₂ emissions by boosting economic development, and Halicioğlu found similar results (2009). Foreign trade, on the other hand, improves environmental efficiency by introducing new technologies into domestic development, according to Shahbaz et al. (2012). In the long run, we discovered that financial growth has an inverse relationship with carbon

emissions. It has been calculated that a 1% rise in DC (domestic credit to private investors) would result in a 0.0012-unit reduction in carbon emissions. It implies that financial growth contributes to the reduction of CO₂ emissions by allowing private banks to give credits to businesses for environmentally friendly technologies and projects. This result is supported by the findings of Tamazian et al. (2009), who discovered that financial growth enables developing countries to introduce modern technologies, environmentally friendly production, and, as a result, large-scale environmental change. Bank loans, on the other hand, help Chinese companies access external finance and increase their investment size, according to Zhang (2011).

Economic growth rises in tandem with increases in CO₂ emissions.

Finally, our findings indicate that foreign direct investment improves environmental degradation. It has been reported that a 1% rise in FDI (foreign direct investment) results in a unit increase in CO₂ emissions. Our findings show that Pakistan's economy does not depend on technology transfer from foreign direct investment to improve environmental quality. Furthermore, the country's weak environmental laws could allow developed countries to relocate their dirty industries here. Our findings are consistent with Jensen (1996); however, Zarsky (1999) pointed out that when multinationals participate in foreign direct investment, they are more likely to pass modern green technology to the host country.

Table.3: Long-run effects of EKC Model

Variable	Coefficient	Probability
Constant	-4.826	0.003
lnGDP	4.619	0.053
lnGDP2	-2.359	0.047
lnE	0.390	0.014
lnDC	-0.116	0.028
lnFDI	0.032	0.004
lnTO	-0.015	0.713

The short-run statistics of EKC research is given in Table (4). The table's results indicate that the short-run dynamics often point to the presence of an EKC (Environmental Kuznets curve) in Pakistan's case.

Table.4 Short-run results of EKC Model

Variable	Coefficient	Probability
CO2(-1)	-0.213	0.262
lnGDP(-1)	6.252	0.009
lnGDP2(-1)	-3.005	0.011
lnE(-1)	1.155	0.001
lnDC(-1)	0.245	0.004
lnFDI(-1)	-0.022	0.010
lnTO(-1)	0.027	0.541

Appendix A shows the results of full time series decomposition using the LMDI1 method for the period 1980-2014. In Appendix B, the results of decomposition after including renewable data are presented. The cumulative effects are presented as

index change in Table 5 and annual percentage growth in Table 6. They are divided into three time periods: 1980-1990, 1990-2000, and 2000-2016. The behaviour effect (C ypc) is the dominant positive effect, as shown by the

cumulative decomposition results for the entire period 1980-2014 (fig. 1). This has been shown in several previous studies. The population effect has a positive effect on overall CO₂ emissions, while the emissions coefficient (C_{emc}) has a minor effect. Between 2000 and 2006, the only factor

that negatively impact the carbon pollution is energy intensity, with the fossil fuel substitution effect having a marginal negative impact. From 1980 to 2016, absolute positive effects outweighed total negative effects, resulting in a rise in total CO₂ emissions.

Table 5 Accumulated Decomposition of Pakistan's energy CO₂ from 1980 – 2016

Years	Δ Ctot	ΔCffse	ΔCint	ΔCypc	ΔCpop	ΔCemc
1980-1990	1.497011	1.010329	0.877285	1.225349	1.378267	1.000065
1990-2000	1.497218	0.995708	0.813555	1.438581	1.284721	1.000052
2000-2016	1.548524	1.017465	0.462611	2.457889	1.338353	1.000115
1980-2016	3.470787	1.023562	0.330175	4.332678	2.369808	1.000232

Table.6 Decomposition of Pakistan's energy CO₂ emissions in annual % growth rates

Years	Δ Ctot	ΔCffse	ΔCemc	ΔCint	ΔCypc	ΔCpop
1980-1990	0.280736	0.013064	3.55E-05	-0.03174	0.009576	0.289802
1990-2000	0.532617	-0.00429	5.24E-05	-0.18645	0.438581	0.284721
2000-2016	1.281550	0.022583	0.000115	-0.53739	1.457889	0.338353
1980-2016	3.183542	0.031496	0.000202	-0.63559	2.569731	1.2177

Figure 2 depicts the complete decomposition for the period 1980-2016; the index reflects the accumulated shift in 2016 from the 1980 base period. According to the results, the activity component has a greater influence on total CO₂ emissions changes. The second largest contributor is population growth; as Pakistan's population increases, the economy requires more energy consumption, necessitating reliance on fossil fuels, resulting in increased CO₂ emissions. Empirical analysis reveals that total CO₂ emissions are influenced negatively by the intensity effect, meaning that total CO₂ emissions have decreased over time as a result of the intensity effect. An increase in production processes, or a decrease in energy intensity, may explain the decrease in energy intensity which can be attributed to energy efficiency, or it can be due to energy shortages in the region, which has resulted in a reduction in energy usage below the level of demand. As a result, the energy level has dropped. Fossil fuel replacement has a benefit of less than one, implying that it has a negative impact on overall CO₂ emissions. This finding can be due to the economy's replacement of natural gas for oil after 2002-03. Since gas is a less carbon-intensive

source of energy, overall CO₂ emissions have decreased to some extent as a result of this energy source substitution.

Both the emission coefficient effect and the fossil fuel replacement effect contribute to limiting emission growth, but these effects are small and disappear when renewable data is included in the decomposition study (fig.4). Table 7 shows the results of the decomposition analysis after adding renewables data for the period 1990-2016, while Table 8 shows the results in annual percentage increase.

Carbon emissions begin to decline between 1990 and 2000, owing to a downturn in economic growth and a reduction in energy intensity. Although the population (C_{pop}) effect appears to be beneficial. Energy crises and energy supply shortages are to blame for the negative effect of energy intensity on emissions levels between 1980 and 2016. Energy demand has not been met in recent years due to a disparity between supply and demand; as a result, energy needs for economic growth have not been met, and energy intensity has decreased.

Figure 1: Accumulated decomposition of Pakistan's energy carbon emissions 1980-2016

Figure 2 Results of decomposition analysis (Emissions in Ktoe)

Figure 3 Results of decomposition analysis (Emissions in Ktoe)

Figure 4 Results of decomposition analysis after including Renewables data.

Throughout the time series 1980-2016, the impact of operation (C ypc) can be seen as the largest contributor, particularly from 2002 to 2008. A significant rise in economic growth resulted in an increase in energy consumption and, as a result, a rapid increase in carbon emissions.

Pakistan has also seen an increase in its population. As the population of the city has grown, so has the demand for energy. The use of fossil fuels to meet energy needs has resulted in a rise in pollution. The second-most significant contributor of CO₂ emissions is the (C pop) effect.

The fossil fuel substitution effect is primarily concerned with the substitution of gas and coal for oil. From 2000 to 2005-06, the cumulative decomposition results show that the (C ffse) effect has been decreasing. This is due to the replacement of natural gas for oil consumption, which has a negative effect on overall emissions over this time span because natural gas is less carbon intensive than oil. However, as a result of

gas load control, the share of oil consumption has begun to grow again, as have the related emissions levels. Pakistan is also shifting away from less polluting fuels like coal. In comparison to the largest effects of operation (C ypc) and population (C pop), the net impact of a shift in fuel mix is marginal.

The energy intensity impact is the third largest contributor to emissions levels. Since 1990, the (C int) effect has been decreasing, causing CO₂ strength to decrease, which is a positive sign for the economy. Improvements in technology and manufacturing processes have resulted in a reduction in intensity.

The emission effect (C emc) is the change in carbon as a result of the unit usage of fossil fuels. For the period 1980-2016, the (C emc) effect has a positive influence on overall emission levels. After 2000, the (C emc) effect began to decline, which can be due to changes in fuel quality and technology.

Table 7: Decomposition of Pakistan's energy CO₂ after including renewables data.

Years	ΔCtot	ΔCffse	ΔCint	ΔCypc	ΔCpop	ΔCemc
1990-2000	1.667299	1.003111	0.806443	1.442481	1.285932	1.111124
2000-2016	1.279128	1.128617	0.481636	2.11560	1.269191	0.876371
1990-2016	2.132689	1.132128	0.388412	3.05171	1.632094	0.973756

Table 8 Decomposition of Pakistan's energy CO₂ emissions in annual % growth rates after including renewables data.

Year	ΔCtot	ΔCemc	ΔCint	ΔCypc	ΔCpop	ΔCffse
1990-2000	0.546468	0.099729	-0.10512	0.257425	0.219497	0.024771
2000-2016	0.279128	-0.12363	-0.51836	1.115601	0.269191	0.128617

1990-2016	0.978131	-0.03623	-0.56899	1.660209	0.547774	0.156574
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5. Concluding remarks and Policy implications

Pakistan's energy usage is highly reliant on natural resources such as oil and gas, which are increasingly depleting and causing environmental issues. Pakistan has abundant coal resources; in the near future, we will be able to make use of these resources by implementing clean coal technology. Furthermore, we should concentrate on energy-saving policies, especially in the industrial sector, by utilizing new technology. Energy efficiency would undoubtedly reduce energy intensity, and as a result, pollution will decrease. Investments in renewable energy projects should also be increased. Environmental legislation and policies must be effectively implemented at both the federal and state levels. In Pakistan, environmental sustainability and research are still unattainable; however, new technology and environmentally friendly projects are critical for long-term development. As a result, an environmental tax, such as a green tax, should be implemented to reduce carbon emissions.

It is proposed that the financial sector establish credits for businesses to finance environmentally sustainable investment plans, and that funds be allocated to the energy sector for the development of renewable energy to ensure a clean environment. In order to steer foreign direct investment into clean and environmentally friendly manufacturing, the government must also develop a reasonable industrial policy. The government can play a positive role in modernizing the industry's structure with new technologies, lowering energy consumption, and creating a more energy-efficient climate.

Focusing on the role of institutions in Environmental Kuznets curve analysis would be very useful for future research. Institutional quality and democracy are two variables that can be used to investigate EKC in order to research the impact of environmental policies on carbon emissions. Finally, since renewable energy data is limited in the decomposition analysis, the study's findings can be greatly improved in the future by using more variables in the renewable energy sources.

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Appendix A

Years	ΔC_{tot}	ΔC_{ffse}	ΔC_{int}	ΔC_{ypc}	ΔC_{pop}	ΔC_{emc}
1980-1981	1.084237	0.996384	0.898723	1.156165	1.03538	1.011468
1981-1982	1.183863	1.039393	0.965709	1.063253	1.03721	1.069479
1982-1983	0.978466	0.994979	1.140685	0.895631	1.036823	0.928394
1983-1984	1.022047	1.030356	0.951331	1.050763	1.034205	0.959491
1984-1985	1.096173	1.034008	1.052846	0.967774	1.033072	1.00713
1985-1986	1.090386	0.987252	1.019045	0.991425	1.033257	1.058011
1986-1987	1.077999	1.001353	1.05206	1.012922	1.033291	0.977669
1987-1988	1.06592	1.060271	0.90912	1.119352	1.03206	0.957226
1988-1989	1.067095	0.981923	1.011763	1.0132	1.030952	1.028283
1989-1990	1.045429	0.770776	1.049043	0.968104	1.028892	1.29802
1990-1991	1.046788	0.983684	0.905224	1.10186	1.027334	1.038506
1991-1992	1.029944	0.995099	0.995525	1.041123	1.026421	0.972898
1992-1993	1.106471	1.026115	0.992915	1.03093	1.02557	1.027159
1993-1994	1.092058	1.011345	1.032709	0.982931	1.025589	1.037223
1994-1995	1.03278	0.984188	0.891932	1.142417	1.025882	1.003867
1995-1996	1.087942	1.044956	1.007979	1.018953	1.025848	0.988141
1996-1997	1.006057	0.945865	1.041583	0.961537	1.025294	1.035823
1997-1998	1.016555	1.005946	1.025703	0.97213	1.024677	0.989061
1998-1999	1.086607	0.988704	1.043823	0.988749	1.024406	1.039492
1999-2000	1.02498	1.020672	0.870464	1.153384	1.023654	0.977128
2000-2001	0.954491	0.971573	1.038405	0.957499	1.021566	0.96722
2001-2002	0.995165	0.995258	1.009785	0.980774	1.019565	0.990255
2002-2003	1.016841	0.984206	0.917178	1.112871	1.018322	0.993994
2003-2004	1.036635	1.035282	0.922822	1.129409	1.017446	0.94425
2004-2005	1.049281	1.115007	0.938605	1.079	1.017171	0.913516
2005-2006	1.091396	0.983794	0.852367	1.193385	1.017744	1.071598
2006-2007	1.060612	0.959862	0.955208	1.075614	1.017958	1.056485
2007-2008	0.996729	1.10989	0.896199	1.079623	1.017868	0.911862
2008-2009	1.015902	0.94631	1.022154	0.972674	1.01806	1.060623
2009-2010	1.027441	1.013293	0.965409	1.028897	1.018441	1.00231
2010-2011	0.992439	0.999144	0.854178	1.155437	1.018613	0.988035
2011-2012	1.02808	1.024557	0.965556	1.025406	1.018854	0.994731
2012-2013	0.990878	0.998591	0.973617	1.010922	1.018976	0.98938
2013-2014	1.045367	1.012355	0.96765	1.011453	1.01956	0.99453
1980-2016	3.495546	1.002942	0.355575	4.223066	2.320488	1.000232

Appendix B

Years	ΔC_{tot}	ΔC_{ffse}	ΔC_{int}	ΔC_{ypc}	ΔC_{pop}	ΔC_{emc}
1990-1991	1.008203	0.983684	0.905223	1.10186	1.027334	0.972898
1991-1992	1.05983	0.995099	0.995525	1.041123	1.026421	0.972898
1992-1993	1.078806	1.026114	0.992915	1.03093	1.02557	1.027159
1993-1994	1.052907	1.011345	1.032709	0.982931	1.02559	1.037223
1994-1995	1.028245	0.984187	0.891932	1.142417	1.025882	1.003867
1995-1996	1.098652	1.044956	1.007979	1.018953	1.025849	0.988141
1996-1997	0.971539	0.945865	1.041583	0.961537	1.025294	1.035823
1997-1998	1.027691	1.005946	1.025703	0.97213	1.024677	0.989061
1998-1999	1.044225	0.988704	1.043823	0.988749	1.024406	1.039492
1999-2000	1.047345	1.020672	0.870463	1.153385	1.023654	0.977128
2000-2001	0.986615	0.971573	1.038405	0.957498	1.021566	0.96722
2001-2002	1.005358	0.995258	1.009785	0.980773	1.019565	0.990255
2002-2003	1.02591	0.984206	0.917177	1.112872	1.018322	0.993994
2003-2004	1.115615	1.035282	0.922821	1.12941	1.017446	0.94425
2004-2005	1.180037	1.115007	0.938605	1.079001	1.017171	0.913516
2005-2006	1.021527	0.983794	0.852367	1.193386	1.017744	1.071598
2006-2007	1.004529	0.959862	0.955208	1.075615	1.017958	1.056485
2007-2008	1.109146	1.10989	0.896199	1.079623	1.017868	0.911862
2008-2009	0.951228	0.94631	1.022154	0.972674	1.018061	1.060623
2009-2010	1.028777	1.013293	0.965409	1.028897	1.018441	1.00231
2010-2011	1.005101	0.999144	0.854177	1.155437	1.018613	0.988035
2011-2012	1.038149	1.024557	0.965555	1.025406	1.018854	0.994731
2012-2013	1.001707	0.998591	0.973616	1.010922	1.018976	0.98938
2013-2014	1.005643	0.985647	0.983452	1.024536	1.019675	0.96875
1990-2016	2.132689	1.132128	0.388412	3.051716	1.632094	0.973756

Appendix C: Diagnostic Tests

The results of J-B test and LM test are given in Table 5.5 and 5.6 respectively. The corresponding P-value “0.55” of the Jarque-Bera value (1.208) in Table 5.5 is > than 0.05 which leads to accept H_0 hypothesis of normality test and we conclude that the error terms are normally distributed.

Normality Test:

H_0 : Residuals are normally distributed

Reject H_0 when P-value < 0.05

Test of Normality

Serial Correlation LM test:

H_0 : no serial correlation among the residuals

Reject H_0 when P value < 0.05

The p value “0.103” is clearly larger than 0.05 in table (C1), so we conclude that the H_0 hypothesis is true and we say that there is no autocorrelation.

Table C1 Test of Serial correlation

Serial Correlation LM Test:			
F-stat	0.486	Prob. F(2,8)	0.632
R-squared	4.549	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.103

Stability Test:

To verify the model's stability, we must plot the CUSUM (cumulative sum of recursive residuals) and the CUSUMSQ (cumulative sum of recursive residuals of square). The graphs below demonstrate that the model is stable, with CUSUMSQ and CUSUM results patterns remaining within critical rejection regions (Fig.C1). The results of the graphs show that our ARDL model's predictions are consistent in the short and long term.

CUSUM and CUSUMSQ test.

Cumulative sum of recursive Residuals

Cumulative Sum of Squares of Recursive Residuals

Heteroscedasticity Test:

H_0 : There is no heteroscedasticity

Reject H_0 when P-value < 0.05

Now we check for heteroscedasticity, in table C2 the observed R squared value “6.55” and its corresponding P-value is 1.000 which is > than 0.05 and it leads to accept the H_0 hypothesis that there is no heteroscedasticity in the data.

Table C2 Test of Heteroscedasticity

Heteroscedasticity Test			
F-stat	2.166	Prob. F(31,10)	0.0982
R-squared	36.55	Prob. Chi-Square(31)	1.000